

ANALYSIS OF FEMALES IN V.WOOLF'S "MRS. DALLOWAY"

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Annotation: In this thesis we have tried to show the meaning underlying in the female social and psychological reality in the novel "Mrs.Dalloway" in the period of the modernism. It explores into the female heroines to study Woolf's special perspective on feminism in the patriarchal society. This thesis examines the nature of author's pioneering literary feminism.

Keywords: fiction, portrait, author's characteristic, femininity.

In literary studies, the term "artistic image" is used in both broad and narrow terms. In the broadest sense, an "artistic image" is any reflection of the creative and creative work of creation. When we refer to animals, objects, events, images of nature, we can understand the meaning of human beings in the literary work. It is only natural that human beings can become the main means of fiction in this way that aims at artistic perception of existence. It is easier to understand and explain this point in the case of large-scale epic works where the leveling of images is evident. All other images (objects, animals, events, etc.) in these works serve to illuminate and deepen the image of man. True, there are some works that do not have the image of man: fairy tales or animal stories, landscape lyrics, and so on. However, they are either figuratively speaking of a person's life, or a person's heart. There are a number of tools in fiction that can be used to create a complete image of a person and to enhance his or her imagination. These include artistic elements such as author's character, portrait, artistic psychology, and character talk. The description given by the writer directly to the image is called "author's characteristic". The description of the author describes the main features of the image's character.[1] Usually the author's characteristic is given in the beginning of the work or in the place where the specific image came into the work. The characteristic of the author gives the reader a comprehensive idea of the character and is important for understanding his subsequent actions and words. Examining it with concrete examples will help us to clarify our purpose. "What a lark! What a plunge! For so it had always seemed to her, when, with a little squeak of the hinges, which she could hear now, she had burst open the French windows and plunged at Bourton into the open air. How fresh, how calm, stiller than this of course, the air was in the early morning; like the flap of a wave; the kiss of a wave;..."[2]

Mrs Dalloway, regarded as a masterpiece of Virginia Woolf, is a novel riddled with themes. Woolf has much to say about society and the post-war changes but a steady underlying theme in the book is feminism, the roles of women of that period and their seeming insignificance. Basically, it is the character of Clarissa Dalloway, her relation with Sally Seton, and other women characters, Miss Kilman, Lucrezia Warren, who are also clustered around Clarissa in different contexts of the novel, through which Woolf reveals the physical as well as the psychological world of womanhood, their dilemmas, subjectivity, sexuality and conditioning in the traditional patriarchal society.

In the novel, Clarissa's relationship with her husband, Richard Dalloway, proved to be a failure. Richard was so preoccupied with politics more than his wife. In response to his loyalty to the social duties of upper-class, he left his wife for a meeting that he did not care about. Again, we find Richard was invited to Lady Bruton's party without his wife. At this Clarissa felt a sense of emptiness and insignificance. Clarissa mocked her husband's attempt at taking a hot water bottle as a substitute for her warmth.

"And if she raised her head she could just hear the click of the handle released as gently as possible by Richard, who slipped upstairs in his socks and then, as often as not, dropped his hot-water bottle and swore! How she laughed!"[3]

In Mrs Dalloway, the terrible influence of patriarchy is effectively portrayed through the presentation of Miss Kilman and Rezia's lives. Both were victims of the cruelty of the social and political doctrine of the English society and their only guilt was that they were merely women. What is really tragic about Rezia is not her husband's insanity or death but the unfriendly manner in which the world treated her. She suffered silently and alone. Even her husband Septimus for whom she left her relatives and country was indifferent to her.

"She was very lonely, she was very unhappy! She cried for the first time since they were married. Far away he heard her sobbing; he heard it accurately, he noticed it distinctively; he compared it to a piston thumping. But he felt nothing. His wife was crying, and he felt nothing."[4]

Apart from these frustrated, lonely women characters, Woolf portrayed the character of Elizabeth Dalloway as an example of the unconventional woman. She lacked the enthusiasm in the trivial feminine society of her mother. She had ambitions to have a career and a professional life. She has planned to be doctor, farmer, or to go into parliament.

Woolf ends the novel with a hope for the new woman. Her point is that women shouldn't lose their femininity, and also shouldn't be limited to it. The woman of

the future embraces her femininity and masculinity and makes a choice of how to use that within herself to achieve fulfilment.

In this manner, differing portrayals of females, whose lives were centered around the city, are presented, showing that whilst modernity afforded new opportunities and allowed women to seek their own independence, the traditional role of the female as a kept woman or otherwise, was still highly accepted.

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